

Dependability Assurance with Symbolic Reasoning in LLM-enabled Systems

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Abstract—The rapid advancement of large language models (LLMs) creates new opportunities in cyber-physical systems, particularly in natural language interaction and decision support. However, the safety-critical nature of these systems requires LLMs to operate in a deterministic, verifiable, and reliable way. The proposed solution in the paper combines the flexibility of LLMs with the deterministic capabilities of formal approaches based on symbolic logic reasoning. The LLMs’ structured outputs generated are processed by a logic reasoning engine capable of handling contradictions, priorities, and fault-tolerance patterns. This validation process enables formally valid and auditable LLM-based decisions, even when different models produce conflicting outputs. The proposed approach is illustrated through case studies that demonstrate practical examples of symbolic evaluation.

Index Terms—large language models, symbolic logic reasoning, fault tolerance

I. INTRODUCTION

Large language models (LLMs) have undergone remarkable advancements [1], and today they offer support in domains like human–machine interaction, natural language understanding, and decision support. They present opportunities in the context of cyber-physical systems (CPSs) [2]. However, the deployment of language models in safety-critical environments is only acceptable if it does not compromise the system’s dependability and deterministic behavior [3].

To make LLMs integrable into such environments, it is necessary to go beyond simple interactive usage and develop solutions capable of formally evaluating, validating, and restricting the model outputs. By their nature, LLMs do not guarantee deterministic, consistent, or explainable responses. In this case, for safety-critical applications, control mechanisms (e.g., guardrail solutions) are essential. Such mechanisms already exist (e.g., NVIDIA’s NeMo Guardrails [4], Llama Guard [5]), which can detect hallucinated responses and can leverage external knowledge bases to validate the responses of LLMs. However, these approaches typically focus on user interaction and do not address the specific requirements of tight integration with CPSs (e.g., representing system states, handling fault-tolerance patterns, or managing priorities).

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In this work, we propose a symbolic logic reasoning solution that combines the flexibility of LLMs with the formal reasoning capabilities of symbolic logic systems (e.g., Answer Set Programming). The key idea is that the LLM generates structured, machine-interpretable predicates from natural language inputs, which are then processed by a logic reasoning engine. The logic layer can also incorporate redundancy, prioritization, and fault-tolerance rules. This architecture enables the LLM not merely to provide suggestions but to operate as part of a higher-level, rule-based control system ensuring deterministic and auditable behavior.

A. Symbolic Logic Reasoning

Guardrail mechanisms and symbolic logic-based reasoning systems share a common goal: supervising and controlling the inputs and outputs of large language models (LLMs). However, they differ in terms of knowledge representation, reasoning capabilities, and system state management.

Guardrail systems primarily focus on filtering, format validation, user experience correction, output safety, and the enforcement of legally mandated constraints [6] (e.g., GDPR). These mechanisms are typically based on imperative rules and logic through regular expressions and structured schema validation. These function as static validation rules. Guard systems do not perform logical inference; if a rule is violated, the process usually halts (following the “fail-fast” principle) with no support for handling exceptions, priorities, or alternatives.

Symbolic reasoning approaches can complement guardrail solutions, offering an additional, formal layer of reasoning providing knowledge-based interpretation, decision support, and formal rule-driven control. This approach enables the explicit representation of knowledge in the form of ontologies, rule patterns, and preferences.

In terms of inference, non-monotonic deductive reasoning can be used to handle changing knowledge bases (e.g., updated system states). It is also possible to generate alternative solutions (e.g., in case of a conflict resolution). This way, it supports the development of preference systems, such as rule weighting and what-if simulations.

From a state-handling perspective, logic reasoning allows for the modeling of causal chains and temporal changes, which is important in dynamic systems where decision outcomes

unfold over multiple steps. It offers auditability and explainability, meaning that every conclusion is traceable via a formal logical pathway back to the input rules and facts.

II. ERRORS OF LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

As LLMs become increasingly powerful, they are being explored as intelligent interfaces and decision-support tools within CPSs [2]. Their ability to process and generate human language makes them promising for tasks such as natural language interaction (e.g., interpreting sensor data described in human terms, interacting with autonomous vehicles, issuing commands, controlling smart environments, and generating action plans). However, they are not perfect, as they can still produce erroneous outputs due to biases in training data, hallucinations (i.e., fabricating false or misleading information), lack of real-time knowledge, and challenges with complex reasoning.

Recent advances allow LLMs to augment their capabilities by accessing external tools (e.g., web search engines, APIs, code execution environments) and sources (e.g., knowledge bases) or domain-specific databases. This external access can help mitigate some of the limitations inherent to their training-based reasoning (e.g., retrieving up-to-date information, performing accurate computations, and verifying generated outputs). However, these tool-augmented systems still depend on the model’s ability to *correctly interpret and integrate the retrieved information*.

LLMs predict text from statistical patterns but lack true understanding, physical grounding, and causal models. This limits their ability to perform common-sense or causal reasoning and affects coherence over long contexts due to input window constraints.

When *generating code*, LLMs rely on the same probabilistic mechanism used for natural language. They generate code token-by-token based on training data patterns but not through execution or testing. Some advanced systems integrate code execution and automated testing to validate or refine generated code. The core model itself does not inherently understand whether the code is correct. As a result, LLMs may still produce code that is syntactically valid but logically incorrect, reference non-existent functions, or introduce subtle bugs.

Another concern is *prompt sensitivity and manipulation*. This means small changes in prompts can lead to vastly different or unpredictable responses. They can be tricked into generating harmful content despite safeguards. However, this is primarily a security concern.

In this paper, we focus on a specific class of errors where LLMs inaccurately reproduce or reason over knowledge that can be validated against an external knowledge base (e.g., ontology-based knowledge) and where these validation requires logical inference capabilities to check the consistency and correctness of generated information. Additionally, we target logic-related errors where the LLM exhibits logical fallacies or contradictions. To identify and mitigate these issues, we propose the use of declaratively defined fault-tolerant patterns, which allow for systematic evaluation and

correction of LLM outputs based on structured knowledge and reasoning rules.

III. EVALUATION WORKFLOW

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed symbolic reasoning pipeline. The system is composed of five main steps: (1) Prompt engineering, (2) LLM execution, (3) Output processing, (4) Symbolic reasoning, (5) Evaluation.

Our contribution lies specifically in the formal logic-based reasoning and evaluation of the LLM outputs. We do not address prompt design, prompt validation, or surface-level output filtering in detail, but for the sake of completeness, we will mention them in this section. Existing guardrail frameworks may handle these processes effectively (e.g., schema enforcement, safety filters, or prompt hardening strategies). In our case, we assume that the LLM responses have been normalized into a structured form that can be immediately used for the reasoning process.

A. Prompt Engineering

Prompt design is a key factor in validating LLM outputs. The clarity and structure of a prompt directly affects response accuracy and consistency. Effective prompts clearly specify the task and expected output format (e.g., requesting a summary, a list, or a structured JSON output). Variations like *zero-shot* (no examples) and *few-shot* (with examples) prompting help test how robustly the model handles rephrased queries.

B. LLM Execution

To safely deploy LLMs in critical systems, it may be necessary to run the same input prompt across multiple, diverse LLMs. This approach introduces redundancy and, when combined with sufficient model diversity, enables cross-comparison of outputs, helping to make more reliable and robust decisions.

Each LLM processes the same or slightly varied prompts, returning individual responses which may differ in content, certainty, or structure. This diversity of reasoning pathways can be leveraged to detect inconsistencies, reinforce consensus, and mitigate the impact of individual model errors.

Selecting the proper LLMs can be a difficult task. Different LLMs interpret prompts uniquely due to their training data, architectures, and underlying fine-tuning strategies. Models can differ in several factors influence the selection (e.g., model size, training data cutoff).

In addition to selecting from existing general-purpose models, it is also possible to train or fine-tune custom LLMs on domain-specific data. This process allows organizations to align a model more closely with their specific terminology, workflows, and requirements. Alternatively, techniques like retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) enable models to access a curated knowledge base during inference without altering the base model itself. Both approaches improve reliability by constraining the model’s responses to relevant and validated information sources, reducing the risk of hallucinations and ensuring better performance in specialized tasks.

Fig. 1. Symbolic Reasoning Pipeline

C. Output Processing and Validation

The third step is output processing and validation, which plays a crucial role in ensuring that the validation process is comprehensive, reliable, and meaningful. This step’s primary goal is systematically gathering outputs generated by different LLMs. The output processing step includes: (1) Schema validation (e.g., CSV, JSON structures, logic fact schemas); (2) Guardrail-based filtering (e.g., excluding uncertain or non-conformant answers); (3) Normalization of outputs into an intermediate representation suitable for reasoning.

During data collection, it is essential to *capture responses from multiple models* while maintaining consistency in execution conditions. This includes standardizing variables such as model versions, temperature settings, sampling techniques, and the structure of the prompts. Without a controlled approach, inconsistencies in data collection could lead to misleading comparisons and hinder the accuracy of validation efforts.

Additionally, *metadata tracking* is critical. Each collected response should be stored alongside relevant contextual information (e.g., prompt used, model and version).

In this paper, we manually checked the format of the LLM outputs and automatically transformed the output CSV data into logic expressions, but full pipeline reliability requires strict output validation.

D. Symbolic Reasoning

In the final step, the normalized outputs produced by the LLMs are passed into the symbolic reasoning module, which performs formal logical inference based on a background knowledge base and predefined domain constraints. This component is responsible for verifying the internal consistency of the outputs, detecting violations of system-specific safety rules, and supporting higher-order reasoning tasks.

The symbolic layer can include reasoning libraries (modules), allowing them to be invoked dynamically based on the type of reasoning (e.g., consistency checking, abductive inference, prioritization, or error propagation analysis) and the fault-tolerant pattern being applied (e.g., majority consensus, exception masking, or fail-safe evaluation).

E. Evaluation

The final output is determined by the Evaluation component, which integrates the conclusions of symbolic inference and, based on system-specific criteria, either returns a trusted decision or triggers fallback handling mechanisms. These may

include human-in-the-loop escalation, prompt reformulation, or the generation of new prompts to re-query one or more LLMs under revised conditions. This ensures that the system can adaptively respond to uncertainty, ambiguity, or detected inconsistencies in a structured and recoverable manner.

Although not explored in this paper, a feedback loop could use the outcomes of logical reasoning to refine future prompts (e.g., by indicating previous errors or adding clarifying constraints). This mechanism could enhance response accuracy, support adaptive prompt strategies.

IV. FAULT TOLERANCE WITH SYMBOLIC REASONING

Our goal is to enable the validation of LLM outputs through a discrete, formal logic apparatus, providing an approach for integrating language models into critical systems while ensuring key dependability attributes.

Dependability [7] represents a critical system property defined by the ability of a system to deliver service that can be justifiably trusted by users, extending far beyond traditional performance metrics. One of the means to attain dependability is *fault tolerance*. Fault tolerance is intended to preserve the delivery of correct service in the presence of active faults. This is done by intervening in the fault-error-failure chain by detecting an error and using resources to perform correction or recovery to provide correct service without failure.

The aim of our approach is to integrate fault tolerance in LLM-enabled CPSs to detect and mitigate errors on the output of the LLM by avoid them causing any failure. We achieve this by validating the responses of LLMs using classic fault-tolerant patterns [8].

The section first introduces Answer Set Programming (ASP) as the declarative reasoning engine supporting the validation process. It then explores how fault-tolerant patterns (redundancy, knowledge base, and logic reasoning) can be integrated into the reasoning pipeline.

A. Reasoning Engine

We selected Answer Set Programming (ASP) for its declarative, nonmonotonic logic capabilities, making it ideal for representing evolving knowledge, resolving conflicts, and representing fault-tolerant rules. ASP enables validation of LLM outputs via precise rule sets, with stable models [9] computed by solvers like Clingo [10]. Its support for incomplete information, preferences, and explainability makes it well-suited for

using it in dependability-critical domains, where the formal correctness is essential.

While alternatives like Prolog, ontology reasoners, and SMT solvers were considered, they each had limitations (e.g., lack of default negation, focusing on satisfiability) whereas ASP provides a well-balanced solution with expressive modeling, preference support, and efficient nonmonotonic reasoning.

ASP supports a wide range of knowledge representation constructs, enabling fine-grained control over both the structure of the knowledge and the reasoning process. At its core are logical rules that combine classical logic with default negation (not) and explicit negation (\neg), enabling the representation of both assumed and observed truths, as well as contradictions.

The base elements of ASP are *atoms*, *literals*, and *rules*. Atoms are elementary propositions that may be true or false. Literals are atoms `atom` and their negations `not atom`. Rules are expressions in the form:

```
rule :- atom_1, ..., atom_i,  
       not atom_j, not atom_n.
```

A rule holds if all its body literals are satisfied: a literal `atom` is true if it has a derivation, and `not atom_j` is true if `atom_j` does not. Facts are "bodyless" rules always considered true: `fact`.

In ASP, constraints can be used to eliminate models that violate domain-specific rules, ensuring that only acceptable solutions are considered. Constraints are special rules with an empty head: `:- rule_1, rule_2`.

ASP supports choice rules for modeling multiple solutions, optional elements, or partial knowledge. They use curly braces, e.g., `1\{p, q\}2.`, meaning at least one and at most two of `p` and `q` must be chosen.

In addition, it supports expressing preferences and optimization criteria, such as selecting the most reliable or minimal explanation among alternatives. This makes it suitable not only for determining valid conclusions, but also for ranking and choosing among multiple plausible solutions. This is done by using *weak constraints*: `~rule. [weight@priority]`

Weak constraints are prioritized using the `priority` parameter. The `weight` parameter sets the penalty per violation of the weak constraint.

Through aggregates such (e.g., `count`, `sum`), ASP enables quantitative reasoning about collections of atoms. For instance: `#count {LLM: result(LLM, _, _, _)}.` counts how many distinct values of `LLM` appear in the `result/4` predicate.

By using these ASP constructs, it is possible to apply various fault-tolerant patterns to validate the outputs of LLMs by using logic reasoning. This section introduces these patterns and demonstrates how they can be expressed in ASP.

B. Redundancy-based patterns

Redundancy consists of having alternate resources (e.g., hardware, software, information, time) that perform the same function to maximize availability. For instance, three sensors can be used instead of one to get reliable readings even if one fails. An implementation for redundancy could be n-modular redundancy, where `n` components are used in parallel to

perform the same function reliably. These redundancy patterns are also particularly useful when LLMs are applied in CPSs (e.g., an AI assistant component) and many of them have to be used to get a robust result. This result is obtained by using consensus strategies to decide what output to accept from redundantly applied components. The most widely used consensus strategy in redundant architectures is *voting*, which also serves as an error detection pattern. This means that when more than one value is available for a computational result, a task, or a measurement, the correct one is picked by voting. For instance, the correct measurement value from 3 redundant sensors is picked by majority voting. Voting and consensus solutions can also be used to select a correct output of multiple LLM-enabled components:

1) *Majority Voting*: The responses are accepted based on a majority decision. If the outputs of more than half of the components match, then that value is accepted. For instance, in a scenario when LLMs are used to diagnose a patient, we can say that the correct diagnosis is flu when 2 out of 3 models diagnose flu based on given symptoms. The ASP code of this example is shown in Listing 1.

```
diagnosis(claude, flu).  
diagnosis(gpt35, flu).  
diagnosis(gpt4, cold).  
  
count(D, N) :- N =  
              #count { LLM : diagnosis(LLM, D) }  
  
% Accepted if 2 of the 3 models agree  
majority(D) :- count(D, N), N > 3/2.
```

Listing 1: Majority voting of flu diagnosis

2) *Weighted Voting*: The outputs of the redundant components are considered in a weighted manner. Considering the previous example, we can assign a weight of 2 to a GPT4-type LLM and a weight of 1 to a GPT3.5-type LLM (see Listing 2). This means that because GPT-4 models are more sophisticated, their responses has a higher proportion. Also internal dependability factors can guide weight assignment. Models with higher *auditability* (e.g., traceable chain-of-thought) or better *domain-specific performance* may receive greater weight. Additionally, non-LLM redundant components (e.g., rule-based modules) can be included with their own weights to strengthen overall reliability.

3) *N-out-of-M Quorum*: A value is acceptable if at least `N` components' output values agree out of `M`. For instance, in an industrial control system, where LLMs are used to assist engineers in diagnosing faults, a conclusion can be drawn that the system is reliable only if at least 2 LLMs state it. This looks like the following in ASP:

```
consensus :- quorum_count(reliable, N), N >= 2.
```

Here `quorum_count(D, N)` is an aggregate, that counts how many LLMs gave the `D` diagnosis.

4) *Conflict Masking*: When there are inconsistencies in the outputs, a warning is generated, or these outputs are excluded. For instance, if two LLMs directly contradict each other a

```

weight(claude, 2).
weight(gpt4_2, 2).
weight(gpt35, 1).

weighted_sum(D, S) :-
    S = #sum { W, LLM :
        diagnosis(LLM, D), weight(LLM, W) }.
total_weight(T) :-
    T = #sum { W, LLM : weight(LLM, W) }.

% Accepted if sum exceeds half of the total weight
majority(D) :-
    weighted_sum(D, S), total_weight(T), S > T / 2.

```

Listing 2: Weighted Voting in ASP

warning is generated that these responses need review. A rule for generating a warning can be the following:

```
warning :- not consensus.
```

C. Knowledge base patterns

Fault observer pattern relies on an observer (or a set of observers) that continuously checks the system’s components for faults and takes corrective actions when necessary. This works with specialized software or hardware modules that continuously monitor the components. When a fault is detected, a response mechanism is triggered that corrects the error if it is possible, makes an alert, or puts the system into a safe mode to prevent damage. The error detection pattern this architecture uses is called *routine audits*, which consists of checking data by a background task to make sure that it is correct.

In our scenario, a fault observer pattern can audit LLM components in CPSs by validating their outputs against external knowledge (e.g., databases or ontologies) using logical reasoning. ASP, with its declarative representation through facts, rules, and constraints, is well-suited for modeling such background knowledge and validating LLM responses.

For example, a table (dataset) can easily be converted into an ASP model by converting the records into ASP facts. Let $S = \{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ be the scheme of a dataset D where A_i is a set of attributes. Let $r = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a record, which is an n -tuple, where v_i represents the value of an attribute. This way a dataset D is a collection of records: $D = \{r_1, \dots, r_m\}$, where m is the number of records. A record can be converted into ASP facts in the following way: `fact(v_1, ..., v_n)`.

A record can also be modelled in ASP in *long form*, which is a way of structuring data where each observation (or property) is represented as a separate row. Note that this format can also be generated or obtained from the first one using ASP rules.

```

prop(v1_name, v1).
prop(v2_name, v2).
...
prop(vn_name, vn).

```

However, there are several limitations to storing data as facts in ASP. For instance, ASP is not compatible with expressions that contain ASP constraining naming or for numerical values a dot (‘.’) or comma (‘,’), so floating or fixed point numbers. Therefore, some form of discretization may be necessary where qualitative models provides a discrete description of the system. Abstraction can introduce uncertain cases. However,

the properties which held in the original, fine-grained model are preserved in the abstract model as well ensuring that what was true remains true under abstraction.

LLMs can also be instructed to format their output according to a specific schema structure. However, to ensure that the generated responses truly adhere to the intended format, a validation step is necessary. This can be implemented using guardrails, which help enforce the consistency in the output.

This way the LLM-generated results can be validated by comparing the LLM-generated ASP facts to the ones in background knowledge:

```

prop(llm, property, value).
prop(background, property, value).
:- prop(llm, P, V), not prop(background, P, V).

```

This constraint ensures that for every `prop(llm, P, V)`, there must be a corresponding `prop(background, P, V)` existing in the background knowledge. The `not` operator here implements negation as failure, meaning that the constraint is triggered when the facts are contradicting.

Model-to-system alignment also has to be checked so that the LLM response will only be accepted if it is consistent with the system architecture. For instance, if the LLM responds “the backup is active”, but there is no such thing in the system, this response should be rejected. In other words, if the LLM outputs a fact: `backup(active)` the background knowledge should contain that there exists a backup component (i.e. `component(backup)`). This is ensured by the following constraint: `:- backup(active), not component(backup)`.

Policy consistency enforcement has to be applied to ensure that LLM-generated responses in CPS align with predefined operational policies and standards by validating outputs against a structured knowledge base. For instance, if an LLM component suggests bypassing a vehicle’s fail-safe mechanism to improve performance, policy consistency enforcement rejects the response because it contradicts ISO 26262 safety objectives, ensuring compliance and system integrity.

D. Logic reasoning-based patterns

Consistency checking in logic reasoning-based validation ensures that LLM-generated responses in CPSs adhere to declarative rules and avoid logical contradictions. Implemented using ASP, this approach systematically verifies whether responses satisfy predefined constraints, such as ensuring that a statement like “Redundancy is present” does not conflict with the absence of a backup system.

Constraint validation ensures that LLM-generated responses comply with formal safety and operational rules. Using logic reasoning this approach enforces constraints such as requiring at least two active components for system redundancy, rejecting responses that violate these conditions. By systematically verifying adherence to predefined constraints, constraint validation enhances CPS dependability and prevents unsafe or inconsistent outputs.

Other use cases of logic reasoning are *semantic invariant checking*, flow-level evaluation in form of a *formal error propagation analysis*.

Invariant checking ensures that LLM-generated responses do not contradict fundamental semantic relationships defined by the system specification or rule set. For example, "If the cooling pump is operating correctly (ok), then the temperature sensor must not be in a `critical_fault` state." This is because, if the pump is functioning properly, there should theoretically be no overheating, so a critical error on the sensor would be contradictory.

Flow-level evaluation means that the system decides whether the generated output can be passed to the execution subsystem. Error propagation analysis (EPA) guided validation consists of simulating what possible outcomes can cause on the system-level. This allows us to show that if the output of the LLM is a control instruction, then its effects can be inferred through an abstract model of the system, making it possible to examine whether the given instruction is executable (e.g., not violating any constraints).

The proposed approach also enables the examination of logical problem solving. A logical problem can be formulated in natural language for the LLM, which can then generate an answer based on this input. The same logical problem can also be represented formally using ASP, allowing a comparison between the LLM's output and the ASP-based solution. This process can be facilitated by using a unified input for both the LLM and ASP. With the help of the CNL2ASP tool [11], problems can be expressed in a Controlled Natural Language (CNL), which serves as input for the LLM and can also be used to generate ASP code.

V. USE CASES

In this section, we present three examples to illustrate the main use cases of validation through logic reasoning. These examples demonstrate the potential of the approach and provide a foundation for tackling more complex tasks.

In the first example, we applied knowledge-based verification. The second example illustrates the redundant use of LLMs, the incorporation of system context, and the handling of uncertainties. The third example introduces a use case for addressing logic reasoning problems.

A. Validation with Background Knowledge

The example is generating a dataset containing some of the key characteristics of countries in Europe. This include the following features: *Country name*, *Capital city*, *Population*, *Area in km²*, *Currency*, *EU membership*, *Official Languages*, *GDP in Billion USD*.

In this use case, large language models (LLMs) are utilized to process and analyze data through a structured workflow. The process begins with a prompt that feeds into the LLM, which generates a table or dataset in CSV format. This data is then passed into an ASP system, where logic reasoning and constraints are applied to validate the results.

In a previous empirical examinations where we compared the accuracy of the generated data with other LLMs, we concluded that Claude 3.7 [12] would be the best candidate for this experiment. So we asked it to list the European countries'

```
Create a dataset, containing all european countries.
Let the features be the following:
Country, Capital, Population, Area_km2, Currency,
EU_Member, Official_Languages, GDP_Billion_USD.
Provide the output in CSV format.
```

Listing 3: Input prompt for the european countries example

characteristics in order to validate them using background knowledge obtained from different datasets.

While formulating the prompt (Listing 3) we wanted to be as precise as possible. We asked the model to create a dataset containing all European countries. It is important to mention that we want *all* countries, otherwise, it is possible to include only some popular ones (as ChatGPT did in one of our enquiries). As a next step, we specified accurately what features we wanted the generated dataset to contain. This is important because the schema of the output dataset has to be known (i.e., which variables it contains) otherwise, we wouldn't be able to accurately compare it to the background knowledge during the validation process. Finally, we specified the output format as a CSV table.

To perform ASP reasoning using this data, we converted this CSV dataset into ASP facts (see Section IV-C).

To ensure the integrity and correctness of the generated data, the Fault Observer pattern is applied. This means, monitoring for potential errors or inconsistencies in the generated data, ensuring that faulty data or processing errors are identified and addressed. This is realized by performing external validation, using background knowledge to cross-check and verify the outputs for accuracy and consistency.

The background knowledge was obtained from different datasets: Global Country Information Dataset 2023 [13], All Countries dataset [14], and the Country Groups dataset [15] that we used to validate the EU membership of the countries. The features that have to be validated were extracted from these datasets and converted into ASP facts.

As the final step, ASP reasoning was used to compare the generated facts containing the dataset to the facts generated by the background knowledge. This was achieved by using a rule that identifies inconsistencies in property values between different language models (LLM) and a background reference for a given country. It checks if the property value P from LLM differs from the reference value associated with the background model. The rule (see Listing 4) ensures that LLM is not the background model itself while flagging discrepancies.

```
pop_error(PROP, LLM, Country, P, P_bgk) :-
prop(LLM, Country, PROP, P),
prop(background, Country, PROP, P_bgk),
LLM != background,
P_bgk != P.
```

Listing 4: Validation Rule using Background Knowledge

The comparison of the LLM-generated dataset and background knowledge on European countries revealed minor numerical differences in GDP, area, and population due to rounding errors. For official languages, the LLM listed all spoken languages, while background knowledge included only the

Context: The temperature of the chemical reactor is measured by a primary sensor, and there is a backup sensor that automatically activates if the primary one fails. The system also includes a controller that determines safe operation based on the data from the sensors.

State: Currently, the primary sensor has failed, but due to a software update delay, the backup sensor is not yet active. Once the update is completed, the backup will activate automatically.

Question: An engineer asks: Is the system currently reliable?

Listing 5: Input prompt for the consensus example

most common one. There was only one mismatch regarding EU membership, because the Czech Republic was labeled as "Czechia" in the background dataset containing EU members. Currency names only varied in capitalization and language (e.g., rubel vs. ruble). Croatia's currency differed due to dataset timing, with the LLM correctly using the Euro, while the background dataset still listed the kuna from 2023. Capital city names showed minor spelling variations, such as "Brussels" vs. "City of Brussels", both of which are correct.

B. Consensus and Conflict Detection

In industrial control systems, ensuring reliable operation is critical. LLMs can assist in diagnosing faults in temperature regulation systems, but their interpretations may vary. To illustrate this, consider a temperature monitoring system in a chemical reactor, which consists of a *primary sensor*, a *backup sensor* that activates automatically upon primary sensor failure, and a *controller* that determines safe operation based on sensor data. When the primary sensor fails, the system should switch to the backup sensor. However, due to a software update delay, the failover process is not immediate.

The LLM prompt (Listing 5) consists of three main parts: context, system state, question. Different LLMs provide different answers:

- 1) LLM1: "Yes, redundancy is ensured." (Optimistic interpretation: focuses on structural redundancy.)
- 2) LLM2: "No, because the backup is not active." (State-based interpretation: evaluates the current state.)
- 3) LLM3: "Yes, if the backup activates in time." (Scenario-based reasoning: considers future conditions.)

These responses reflect different types of uncertainty: (1) *Structural uncertainty*: A backup sensor exists; (2) *State uncertainty*: The backup is currently operational; (3) *Future uncertainty*: The backup will activate in time.

To formally evaluate these responses, we employed the ASP code described in Listing 6. This decision logic ensures that if at least two LLMs classify the system as reliable without contradiction, the final verdict is `reliable`. If there is a direct conflict (one LLM says "reliable" while another says "not reliable"), the verdict is `need_review`. If the only supporting re-

```
llm(1, reliable).
llm(2, not_reliable).
llm(3, conditional_reliable).

majority_reliable :-
    #count { I : llm(I, reliable) } >= 2.
conflict :-
    llm(_, reliable), llm(_, not_reliable).

final(reliable) :-
    majority_reliable, not conflict.
final(need_review) :- conflict.
final(conditionally_reliable) :-
    llm(_, conditional_reliable), not conflict.
```

Listing 6: ASP code for the consensus example

sponse is conditional, the verdict is `conditionally_reliable`, triggering a warning state.

This approach enables a structured way to validate LLM responses in critical environments, ensuring that logical inference rather than isolated judgments.

C. Logic Problem Solution

In this use case, a logic problem is initially defined in Controlled Natural Language (CNL), a structured form of natural language designed to reduce ambiguity. The problem is then passed to a large language model (LLM), which interprets the logic and provides a solution in a structured format. This enables the LLM to automatically solve the problem and present the result in a way that is easily interpretable.

Simultaneously, the logic problem is converted into Answer Set Programming (ASP) using the CNL2ASP [11] tool, which translates the CNL definition into a formal representation. The ASP problem is then solved using the Clingo solver.

Finally, the solutions from both the LLM and ASP are compared. This comparison allows for validation of the LLM's output against the more formal, logic-based solution provided by the ASP system, ensuring that the LLM's interpretation of the problem aligns with the expected logical reasoning.

In our experiments, we solved the graph coloring problem using ASP and three LLMs, which was an example used in [11]. This consists of given a complete graph with three nodes and given three colors. The graph's nodes have to be assigned colors in a way that two connected nodes must not have the same colors. In this case, ChatGPT and Gemini solved the problems correctly. Claude, on the other hand, misinterpreted the problem and solved it incorrectly. It misinterpreted the specification of relationships between the vertices of the graph and performed the colouring on multiple different graphs. After a second run, its results were correct, but the reasoning behind it was incorrect.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The application of LLMs in CPSs requires deterministic, reliable, and auditable operation due to the safety-critical nature of these environments. However, LLMs do not guarantee consistent or deterministic outputs and are prone to generating incorrect, hallucinated, or logically flawed responses.

The paper introduced a solution that combines the flexibility of LLMs with the formal and deterministic capabilities of symbolic logic-based reasoning systems.

In the proposed validation workflow, LLMs generate structured, machine-readable predicates that are processed by a logic engine capable of handling priorities, redundancy, and fault-tolerance patterns. To further enhance reliability, the system evaluates and compares outputs from multiple LLMs using consensus-based or rule-driven strategies.

The integration of ASP supports the efficient computation of stable models while incorporating preferences, optimization criteria, and non-monotonic reasoning. By aligning LLM-generated outputs with external knowledge, the system can systematically detect inconsistencies and errors.

The approach can incorporate fault-tolerant validation patterns, including: (1) Redundancy-based strategies, which compare outputs from multiple LLMs to reach consensus; (2) Knowledge base validation, which cross-checks model responses against external structured data; (3) Logic-based reasoning, which ensures consistency through the enforcement of formal rules and semantic invariants. Furthermore, it allows the validation of logic problems, solved by both LLMs and ASP.

While logic reasoning-based validation is particularly effective in detecting formal inconsistencies in LLM-generated outputs, its applicability must be clearly scoped. In systems with fully specified declarative rules, the role of LLMs may not be to generate novel solutions, but rather to serve as a flexible interface for interpreting human input and translating it into machine-interpretable forms. In such settings, symbolic validation ensures that any outputs derived from LLMs remain compliant with system-level constraints and do not introduce unexpected behavior.

Importantly, not all hallucinations result in direct logical contradictions. However, hallucinations that do violate constraints (e.g., referencing nonexistent components or generating state-inconsistent assertions) pose significant risks. These are the cases where consistency checking using formal methods is valuable. It allows the system to filter out invalid outputs, enforce operational policies, and ensure that all decisions are auditable and traceable to declarative knowledge sources.

A. Future Work

The proposed symbolic validation framework opens several promising directions for future research. First, beyond EPA, the use of automatic Systems Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA)-based [16] analysis could enhance the evaluation of control instructions by assessing their system-level consequences based on control flow representations.

In scenarios involving redundant LLMs, it is valuable to investigate cases where models generate executable code (e.g., N-version programming). Through static analysis and abstract interpretation, a verifiable representation can be derived, enabling discrete verification. Furthermore, by treating the generated code as a black-box component, input-output behavior can be analyzed and integrated into an impact assessment workflow to evaluate the consequences of potential faults.

Another promising direction is the implementation of a feedback loop, where symbolic reasoning results influence prompt generation or even model fine-tuning. This would support a "learn from logic" architecture, allowing symbolic logic to guide LLM behavior.

From the knowledge representation perspective, exploring ontology-driven prompting could help adapt LLM inputs to align more closely with the system's internal knowledge base, thereby improving output consistency and accuracy.

It will also be valuable to explore the analysis of Chain-of-Thought (CoT) reasoning [17], as it offers insight into the model's internal thought process. For instance, a reasoning-based solution could verify the claims made in the CoT or even complement them. Furthermore, there is potential for formal verification of CoTs meaning that if a CoT makes a claim, it can be validated against background knowledge.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Achiam, S. Adler, S. Agarwal, L. Ahmad, I. Akkaya, F. L. Aleman, D. Almeida, J. Altenschmidt, S. Altman, S. Anadkat *et al.*, "Gpt-4 technical report," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.08774*, 2023.
- [2] W. Xu, M. Liu, O. Sokolsky, I. Lee, and F. Kong, "Llm-enabled cyber-physical systems: Survey, research opportunities, and challenges," in *2024 IEEE International Workshop on Foundation Models for Cyber-Physical Systems Internet of Things (FMSys)*, 2024, pp. 50–55.
- [3] Y. Dong, R. Mu, G. Jin, Y. Qi, J. Hu, X. Zhao, J. Meng, W. Ruan, and X. Huang, "Building guardrails for large language models," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.01822*, 2024.
- [4] T. Rebedea, R. Dinu, M. Sreedhar, C. Parisien, and J. Cohen, "Nemo guardrails: A toolkit for controllable and safe llm applications with programmable rails," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.10501*, 2023.
- [5] H. Inan, K. Upasani, J. Chi, R. Runqta, K. Iyer, Y. Mao, M. Tontchev, Q. Hu, B. Fuller, D. Testuggine *et al.*, "Llama guard: Llm-based input-output safeguard for human-ai conversations," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.06674*, 2023.
- [6] S. Asthana *et al.*, "Deploying Privacy Guardrails for LLMs: A Comparative Analysis of Real-World Applications," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.12456*, 2025.
- [7] A. Avizienis, J.-C. Laprie, and B. Randell, "Fundamental concepts of dependability," *Department of Computing Science Technical Report Series*, 2001.
- [8] R. Hanmer, *Patterns for Fault Tolerant Software*. Wiley Publishing, 2007.
- [9] I. Niemelä, P. Simons, and T. Sojininen, "Stable model semantics of weight constraint rules," in *Logic Programming and Nonmonotonic Reasoning: 5th International Conference, LPNMR'99 El Paso, Texas, USA, December 2–4, 1999 Proceedings 5*. Springer, 1999.
- [10] M. Gebser, R. Kaminski, B. Kaufmann, and T. Schaub, "Multi-shot asp solving with clingo," *Theory and Practice of Logic Programming*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 27–82, 2019.
- [11] S. Caruso, C. Dodaro, M. Maratea, M. Mochi, and F. Riccio, "Cn2asp: converting controlled natural language sentences into asp," *Theory and Practice of Logic Programming*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 196–226, 2024.
- [12] Anthropic, "Claude: Ai assistant," 2024, large language model developed by Anthropic. [Online]. Available: <https://www.anthropic.com>
- [13] N. Elgiriye withana, "Global country information dataset 2023," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/dsv/6101670>
- [14] A. Kishor, "All countries_details," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/adityakishor1/all-countries-details>
- [15] O. C. Data, "Country groups dataset," 2024, accessed: 2025-03-28. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/openclimatedata/countrygroups>
- [16] T. Ishimatsu, N. G. Leveson, J. Thomas, M. Katahira, Y. Miyamoto, and H. Nakao, "Modeling and hazard analysis using stpa," 2010.
- [17] Y. Chen, J. Benton, A. Radhakrishnan, J. U. C. Denison, J. Schulman, A. Somani, P. Hase, M. W. F. R. V. Mikulik, S. Bowman, J. L. J. Kaplan *et al.*, "Reasoning models don't always say what they think."